

Supplementary Material for: Summary tests of introgression are highly sensitive to rate variation across lineages

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Type-1 error rate with residual rate variation across edges

Figure S1: Type-1 error rate when $h = 0$ as in Fig. 5, but in the presence of residual rate variation across edges.

Figure S2: Type-1 error rate when $h \geq 1$ but $h' = 0$ as in Fig. 6, but with residual rate variation across edges.

Power when $h > 0$ or with residual rate variation

Figure S3: Power to detect the presence of reticulations depending on the number of hybridizations h' after iteratively shrinking 2- and 3-cycles as in Fig. 7, but in the presence of residual rate variation across edges.

Figure S4: Power to detect the presence of reticulations for D , D_3 , and HyDe, depending on the number of hybridizations h in the 3-taxon ingroup network before iteratively shrinking 2- and 3-cycles, in the absence of residual rate variation across edges. Each point represents the proportion of tests with a p-value below 0.05 across four-taxon subnetworks sharing the same number of hybridizations in the ingroup (h) from 100 simulated networks, with an average of 2193 four-taxon subnetworks per point when $h = 1$, 469 subnetworks per point when $h = 2$, and 100 subnetworks per point when $h \geq 3$. Color and point shape are as in Fig. 5.

Figure S5: Power to detect the presence of reticulations depending on the number of hybridizations h as in Fig. S4, but in the presence of residual rate variation across edges.